

ICPEs 2025

40th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON PRODUCTION ENGINEERING - SERBIA 2025

DOI: [10.46793/ICPEs25.279P](https://doi.org/10.46793/ICPEs25.279P)

Nis, Serbia, 18 - 19th September 2025

HOW THE LOLA 8A COMPUTER WAS MADE — A REVERSE ENGINEERING STUDY

Stevan PAROJČIĆ¹, Dragan PAVLOVIĆ^{1*}

Orcid: 0000-0003-2299-0579

¹ Lola Institute, Kneza Višeslava 70A, 11030 Belgrade, Serbia

*Corresponding author: pavlovic.dragan74@gmail.com

Abstract: *This paper presents the reconstruction process of the domestic microcomputer Lola 8A, originally developed in the early 1980s at the "Ivo Lola Ribar" Institute. Through reverse engineering, the original device hardware was analyzed, its functional units mapped, and a working replica of the computer system was built using modern tools and replacement components. Special emphasis was placed on preserving the original architecture, the behavior of the software environment, and compatibility with peripheral units. The process involved creating a new motherboard and reviving the ROM environment by implementing a BASIC interpreter, a monitor program, and a mini-assembler. The device was successfully tested using controlled environments and original applications, although very few of the latter have survived. This project not only reconstructed a significant example of domestic technological heritage but also laid the foundation for educational use, museum exhibits, and the development of modernized platforms based on open hardware principles.*

Keywords: *Lola 8A, Reverse Engineering, Intel 8085 Microprocessor, BASIC Interpreter, Digital Technological Heritage, Retro Computers.*

1. INTRODUCTION

At a time when microcomputers were beginning to conquer the world, the 'Ivo Lola Ribar' factory from Železnik made a significant leap forward — in the early 1980s, it started developing its computer system, the Lola 8. This device represented one of the first attempts in the former Yugoslavia to construct a functional, affordable, and technically competitive microcomputer, intended for a broad range of users, from educational institutions and industrial automation to household use as a home computer.

Unlike domestically produced computers such as the Pecom, the Lola 8A gives the impression of significantly more robust and reliable construction, both in terms of component selection and overall design approach. Architecturally and structurally, its quality and integration logic resemble higher-tier Western systems such as the BBC Model B or Apple II, featuring an efficient switched-mode power supply, a compact enclosure, and a high-quality keyboard, marking a substantial advancement over domestic standards of that time. Lola 8a represents one of the brightest achievements of the domestic industrial electronics of that period.

Motivated by the technical significance of this computer and its place within the domestic technological heritage, Author (1) conducted a complete reconstruction of the Lola 8A computer in 2023 using reverse engineering. Author (2) also participated in the project, providing additional analytical and technical support.

This endeavor encompassed the physical and functional analysis of the remaining operational device, the development of a new motherboard, the replacement of obsolete components, as well as the revitalization of the software environment. The ultimate goal was multifaceted: functional replication, process documentation, educational demonstration, and a contribution to the preservation of domestic engineering heritage, with genuine potential for future applications.

2. THE ORIGINAL LOLA 8A COMPUTER — A TECHNICAL REVIEW

The Lola 8A computer, developed in the early 1980s within the 'Ivo Lola Ribar' Institute, represented one of the first domestic attempts to create a microcomputer system intended for industrial and educational applications. Radovan Novaković authored the hardware design, while Nela Ristanović developed the software part [1].

The Lola 8A was developed as a derivative model of systems based on the Intel 8085 microprocessor, which was primarily used at the Institute for industrial CNC machines and robotics [2]. The Intel 8085, operating at a clock speed of 5 MHz, provided essential control and logical functions in real time. The memory configuration included 6 KB of static RAM (type 6264), with the possibility of expansion up to 38 KB, which at the time represented a considerable investment due to the high cost of memory. The ROM memory totaled 12 KB, expandable to 16 KB, and contained a built-in BASIC interpreter, allowing for direct programming without the need for external tools.

In the domain of video subsystems, the advanced HD46505SP video controller (also known as the CRTC – Cathode Ray Tube Controller) was used, providing a graphical resolution of 75×80 pixels and a text mode of 40×25 characters. This chip was comparable to those used in computers such as the BBC Micro and Amstrad CPC, placing the Lola 8A among the more powerful graphics platforms of domestic production.

The audio subsystem was based on the popular AY-3-8910 chip, which enabled three independent tones across an eight-octave range and was widely used in the microcomputer industry of the time. However, this chip has become increasingly difficult to source in recent years.

The computer featured a 48-key alphanumeric keyboard, and all subsystems—from power supply to peripheral units—were housed in a compact, integrated enclosure with switched-mode power supply, representing an advanced design decision compared to the then-dominant solutions relying on bulky transformers.

Table 1. Detailed Overview of Lola 8A Computer Specifications

Component	Specification
Processor (CPU)	Intel 8085A @ 4.9 MHz
Random Access Memory (RAM)	16 KB (expandable up to 32 KB)
ROM	12 kB, expandable to 16 kB, with BASIC interpreter
Video controller	HD46505SP(CRTC), graphics 75 x 80 pixels, text 40 x 25 characters
Audio chip	AY-3-8910, three tones, eight octave range
Keyboard	Alphanumeric, 48 buttons
Housing	Compact, integrated with switching power supply
Extensions	64-pin EURO connector (A/D, I/O, serial interfaces)
Intended	Industry, CNC systems, education

3. REVERSE ENGINEERING PROCESS

For expansion purposes, the system featured a 64-pin EURO connector, which allowed for the connection of additional modules such as A/D converters, I/O units, and serial/communication interfaces. Among other notable components were the SAB8226 used as a buffer chip—a relatively rare element today—and a large number of standard TTL integrated circuits. Notably, the ULA (Uncommitted Logic Array), which was commonly used in many computers of that era, was not implemented, simplifying servicing and enabling easier replacement of individual components. A detailed overview of the Lola 8A computer specifications is presented in Table 1.

Reverse engineering represents a methodological approach to the analysis and reconstruction of an existing device or system to understand its structure, functionality, and mode of operation, especially in cases where the original technical documentation is unavailable or incomplete.

There is very little information in the literature regarding the mentioned computer. In the context of reconstructing the “Lola 8a” computer, this process was essential for identifying components, mapping interconnections, and enabling future replication of the system.

Given that the Lola Institute possesses the original version of the Lola8a computer, the first step in the process was a physical inspection and analysis of the device. This included careful disassembly and identification of all components, with special attention given to preserving the original connections and traces on the printed circuit board (PCB). Based on visual inspection and the layout of elements, a preliminary schematic of interconnections was created using the KiCad 7.0 software [3]. A detailed list of problematic connections was also compiled, after which testing began.

Figure 1. Connection diagram in KiCad 7.0 software package

During the process, the following tools and methods were used:

Logic analyzer – utilized for monitoring digital signals, detecting errors, and analyzing communication protocols between digital components such as chips.

Oscilloscope – used to measure both analog and digital voltages. Particularly useful for verifying clock signals and bus activity, as well as for checking the operation of chips and other elements.

Figure 2. Verification of the operation of elements with the help of an oscilloscope

Micro-analysis – used for detailed visualization of traces and connections on the printed circuit board (PCB), identification of components with unclear markings, as well as for analyzing internal layers in multilayer boards without causing physical damage.

Numerous challenges hindered the reverse engineering process for the computer:

Lack of detailed technical documentation – the analysis required a deductive approach,

relying on scarce information from the available manual for the Lola 8a computer and comparisons with architecturally similar systems.

Inactive or damaged chips – dynamic testing during operation was not possible, so the chips were subjected to static analysis of pins, current paths, and logical connections in order to determine their function and potential interactions within the hardware architecture.

The search for original components – involved an extensive investigation through old electronic devices of a compatible generation, followed by careful disassembly and testing of preserved and functional parts.

Sourcing replacement parts – particularly for specific components that are no longer in production, which required searching for functional equivalents. However, some elements had to be repurposed from old computers, such as the 7404 inverter.

All steps were carefully documented—including photographs, schematics, measurements, and notes—to facilitate future reconstruction of the device and support the education of other researchers and enthusiasts. This approach not only contributes to the transparency of the work but also serves as a foundation for the potential creation of a functional replica of the Lola 8a.

4. DEVICE RECONSTRUCTION AND TESTING

The reconstruction process of the Lola8a computer required a careful combination of engineering expertise, research, and enthusiasm. At this stage of the project, the focus was on the precise reconstruction of the hardware assembly, revitalization of the software part, and thorough detail functionality testing to achieve a faithful replica of the original system.

The initial step involved designing a new motherboard using the KiCad 7.0 software for PCB layout. Photographs and manually recorded layouts from the original Lola8a device served as references. After finalizing the design, the board was manufactured by JLC PCB. Component soldering was carried out

carefully and manually, with special emphasis on preserving the original system logic. Components that are no longer available were replaced with modern equivalents, following prior compatibility testing.

Alongside the physical reconstruction, the revival of the software component was carried out.

As a brief overview of the Lola ROM, in addition to BASIC, both a monitor program and a mini-assembler were implemented, enabling easier manipulation and correction of machine programs. Embedding monitor and assembler programs into the computer's ROM had not been practiced until now, although similar implementations were observed in Acorn's BBC system. It should be noted that it is not possible to run both the assembler and BASIC simultaneously; the system operates in one of the modes—either monitor or BASIC [4].

The keyboard and monitor are connected using converter units that translate signals into a format compatible with modern devices, while preserving the logic of the original interaction. The computer replica has been successfully integrated with several original peripheral components, including period-specific keyboards, CRT monitors, and external storage (cassette tapes). Through a series of adapters and electronic interfaces, communication between the replica and these units was enabled without compromising functionality.

The final stage of the project involved intensive system testing under controlled conditions. Test programs were executed, including examples written in the BASIC language, to verify input/output functionality. Industrial applications that were once used on Lola8a systems, where available, were run in an emulated environment due to the lack of additional original hardware. The only preserved game operated flawlessly. Results demonstrated a high level of accuracy and reliability compared to the original system. The computer's stability was tested through continuous operation for more than 48 hours without errors, confirming the quality of the reconstructed system.

Figure 3. Testing the Lola8a device

To verify the functionality of the developed software environment for the Lola 8a replica, basic real-time system tests were conducted. The testing focused on confirming proper initialization of hardware resources, execution of basic instructions, and operation of input-output (I/O) modules.

The entire process has been thoroughly documented through technical reports, reconstruction photographs, video demonstrations of the system's operation, as well as a digital archive of software components. This ensures the project's lasting value for future research, educational purposes, and the preservation of domestic technological heritage.

5. CONCLUSION

By implementing a replica of the Lola 8a computer, a significant example of domestic digital technology from the mid-1980s was successfully reconstructed. The project encompassed the entire process of reverse engineering, identification of hardware

functional units, and the development of new technical documentation.

The result holds multifaceted value: as an educational tool for studying the fundamentals of digital systems, as an exhibit for museum and academic presentations, and as a foundation for the development of modernized versions based on FPGA technology or open-source hardware.

Potential applications include data acquisition, control of basic CNC systems, and development of mini educational platforms ('Mini Lola'), thereby positioning the project within the domain of contemporary technical practice.

The expertise acquired during the project is readily applicable to tasks involving the restoration, analysis, and interpretation of vintage computer systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200066).

REFERENCES

- [1] Dejan Ristanović, Home Computers Made in Serbia (PDF, original in Serbian).
- [2] LOLA Computer Factory, LOLA8A User and Programming Manual, Belgrade, 1986 (original in Serbian).
- [3] Lola8a blog, available at: <https://lola8a.blogspot.com/>, accessed: 08.07.2025.
- [4] Computer World, Our Test: Lola 8A at Home and in School, September 1987 (original in Serbian).